

TABLE 1—SHIFT STUDIES ON *n*-HEXANOL, *p*-FLUOROANILINE BY Pr(pfp)₃, Pr(hfh)₃, Sm(pfp)₃ IN CDCl₃ (1 ml)

Sl. No.	Shift reagent	Nucleophile	Ratio of wt. in mg. (Shift reagent : nucleophile)	Time hr	Position of different signals in δ ppm				
					-OH	-CH ₂ attached to -OH (CH ₂) ₄	OH	-NH ₂	Aromatic protons
1.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	Control	1	4.5	3.55	1.4	0.9	
2.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	5 : 1	2	2.0	3.15	1.15	0.75	
3.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	5 : 1	72	2.0	3.15	1.15	0.75	
4.	Pr(hfh) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	Control	1	4.5	3.55	1.4	0.9	
5.	Pr(hfh) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	5 : 1	2	3.1	3.5	1.35	0.9	
6.	Pr(hfh) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	5 : 1	24	3.75	3.5	1.3	0.9	
7.	Pr(hfh) ₃	<i>n</i> -Hexanol	6 : 1	26	3.75	3.5	1.3	0.9	
8.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	Control	1					3.5 6.8-7.0
9.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	3 : 1	1					2.95 6.4-7.0
10.	Pr(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	3 : 1	24					2.90 6.4-7.0
11.	Sm(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	Control	1					3.5 6.3-7.0
12.	Sm(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	3 : 1	1					3.65 6.5-7.1
13.	Sm(pfp) ₃	<i>p</i> -Fluoroaniline	3 : 1	2					3.75 6.4-7.2

pfp = 4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato.

hfh = 4,4,5,5,6,6,6-heptafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-hexanedionato.

in OH was $\Delta\delta$ 2.5, CH₂ attached to -OH was 0.40, (CH₂)₄ 0.25 and CH₃ by 0.15 ppm. Positions of resonance signals remained unaltered after a long interval of time.

Shift produced by [4,4,5,5,6,6,6-heptafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-hexanedionato]praseodymium(III) with *n*-hexanol was downfield when the spectrum was taken after 2 hr. The following changes were noticed; -OH resonance signal shifted by $\Delta\delta$ 1.4, CH₂ attached to -OH by 0.05, (CH₂)₄ by 0.05 ppm and the CH₃ resonance signal remained unaltered. But when the same spectrum was taken after 24 hr, the position of -OH and (CH₂)₄ shifted by $\Delta\delta$ 0.65 and 0.1 ppm, respectively.

Upfield shift was produced by [4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]praseodymium(III) with *p*-fluoroaniline. Shift at the amino group was $\Delta\delta$ 0.6 ppm, while the shift produced for aromatic protons was very small, 0.1 ppm.

Downfield shift was produced by [4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]-samarium(III). Amino group resonance signal shifted by $\Delta\delta$ 0.15 and aromatic resonance signals by 0.2 ppm after 1 hr.

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Thiazolo[2',3' : 3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]-quinazolin-10-ones

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DIVERSE medicinal properties of thiazole derivatives¹⁻⁴ have prompted many synthetic chemists to prepare new compounds in which this ring is fused with other biologically important nuclei. It is with this aim that synthesis of thiazolo[2',3' : 3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-10-one has been undertaken. The importance of triazole and quinazolinone is well known. The synthesis has been achieved as described below.

3-Amino-2-mercaptoquinazolin-4(3H)-one (I) on condensation with allyl isothiocyanate (II) gave rise to 3-allyl-1-[2-mercapto-4-oxo-3(4H)quinazoliny]-2-thiopseudourea (III), the structure of which finds support from pmr, analytical results and physical characteristics. In its pmr (CDCl₃+TFA) in δ scale, III showed a multiplet (2H), because of the allylic splitting, at 4.16 assignable to two allylic protons (-CH₂-CH=). It also exhibited another multiplet (2H) at 5.35-5.60 which could be attributed to two vinylic protons (-CH=CH₂). One vinylic proton (-CH=CH₂) and the four aromatic protons appeared as multiplets at 5.76-6.00 and 7.85-8.70, respectively. Moreover, the compound was soluble in aqueous NaOH and got reprecipitated on treatment with HCl indicating the presence of mercapto group in position 2. Treatment of III with bromine in glacial acetic acid resulted in the formation of 2-bromomethyl-2,3-dihydro-10H-thiazolo[2',3' : 3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-10-one (IV). The structure (IV) again has been confirmed on the basis of pmr data and analytical results. In its pmr (CDCl₃+TFA), IV showed a multiplet (5H) at 3.72-4.70 due to overlapping of signals of two methylene protons of bromomethyl group (-CH₂Br), one

methine proton at position 2 ($-\text{CH}_2-\overset{|}{\text{C}}\text{H}-\text{CH}_2\text{Br}$) and two methylene protons at position 3

($-\text{CH}_2-\overset{|}{\text{C}}\text{H}-$) of the thiazolidine ring. The four aromatic protons also appeared as a multiplet at 7.20–8.70.

Dehydrohalogenation of IV finally gave rise to the required 2-methylene-3H,10H-thiazolo[2',3':3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-10-one (V). Structure V to this compound has been assigned on the basis of ir and analytical results. In its ir, it showed a band at 890 cm^{-1} due to exocyclic carbon-carbon double bond. Besides, it also showed a band at 1670 cm^{-1} due to cyclic amide.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in liquid paraffin bath and are uncorrected. IR spectrum was taken on Perkin Elmer grating IR spectrometer 621 in Nujol. PMR spectra were recorded on Varian EM-390 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal reference.

3-Allyl-1-(2-mercapto-4-oxo-3(4H)quinazolinyl)-2-thiopseudourea (III): A mixture of allyl isothiocyanate (0.30 g) and 3-amino-2-mercaptoquinazolin-4(3H)-one⁶ (0.5 g) was heated on a steam bath for 2 hr. The solid mass was triturated with ethanol (1 ml) and collected under suction. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 210° , yield 0.68 g (90%). (Found: N, 19.42. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{OS}_2$ requires N, 19.18%).

2-Bromomethyl-2,3-dihydro-10H-thiazolo[2',3':3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-10-one (IV): A solution of bromine (0.26 ml) in glacial acetic acid (1 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring to a cold solution of III (0.152 g) in 10 ml of the same solvent. The contents were kept at room temp. overnight and then heated on a water bath for 1 hr. It was cooled and the product collected under suction. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 240° , yield 0.123 g (70%). (Found: C, 43.37; H, 2.90. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{BrN}_4\text{OS}$ requires C, 43.03; H, 2.67%).

2-Methylene-3H,10H-thiazolo[2',3':3,4]-s-triazolo[5,1-b]quinazolin-10-one (V): 2% Alcoholic potassium hydroxide was added to a solution of IV (0.1 g) in ethanol at 40° . This temp. was maintained for about 20 min. Ice was added to it after cooling to room temperature. The solid product so

obtained was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 220° , yield 0.032 g (42%). (Found: C, 56.00; H, 3.24. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{OS}$ requires C, 56.25; H, 3.12%).

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Experiments with Coumarins. Part-I :

Synthesis of 3,5-Disubstituted Isoxazoles and Pyrazoles

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1-Coumaryl-3-arylpropane-1,3-diones and γ -pyrones of coumarins possess physiological activities¹⁻³. Isoxazole derivatives are important as potential antibacterial⁴, antitubercular⁵ and antiviral agents. In view of this, interest in the synthesis of these compounds developed considerably. Present work deals with the synthesis of isoxazoles (II, III), pyrazoles (IV, V) and γ -pyrones (VI, VII) of coumarins.

o-Hydroxyacetyl coumarins were used as starting materials. 7-Hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin and 5-hydroxy-6-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin were prepared according to literature⁷⁻¹¹. Esters of *o*-hydroxyacetyl coumarins were prepared by esterification with aromatic acids. These esters, on Baker-Venkataraman transformation, were converted to 1-coumaryl-3-arylpropane-1,3-diones (I). 3,5-Disubstituted isoxazoles (II, III) and pyrazoles (IV, V) were prepared by refluxing the mixture of propane-1,3-diones (I) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, respectively. Propane-1,3-diones (I) cyclized to afford γ -pyrones (VI, VII) in acetic acid medium.

IR spectra of isoxazole showed absorption bands at $1645\text{--}1650$ ($\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{O}$), 940 ($=\text{N}-\text{O}$) and 840 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$).